

Employee Attrition Prediction Using Machine Learning Classification

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Abstract : The loss of good employees is a key concern for any company, since it may have a negative impact on efficiency, morale, and results. This research proposes a machine learning approach to forecasting employee turnover in an effort to address the issue. The primary objective is to analyze the factors that influence employee turnover so that businesses may develop effective retention strategies. Data Preprocessing with Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Feature Extraction with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Classification with three distinct algorithms: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting are the four key components of the proposed technique. RFE is used in the Data Preprocessing step to identify the most relevant characteristics from the employee dataset. RFE eliminates less important features recursively, resulting in a smaller feature set while maintaining the most informative ones. Following that, feature extraction is conducted using PCA to improve the model's prediction potential. PCA reduces the original feature space to a lower-dimensional space, ensuring that the newly generated features capture the greatest amount of variation in the data. Finally, three classification techniques are used to predict employee attrition: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting. These algorithms were selected because of their ability to handle binary classification problems as well as their complementing skills in dealing with various kinds of input and decision limits.

Keywords: Employee Attrition Prediction, Recursive Feature Elimination, Machine Learning, Principal Component Analysis

I. Introduction

Organizations have considerable hurdles in maintaining their prized staff in today's fast-paced and competitive business world . Employee attrition, the phenomena of individuals leaving their positions willingly, may have a negative impact on a company's productivity, stability, and overall performance. Understanding and anticipating employee churn is critical for firms looking to

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keep a talented and engaged team . Traditional approaches of assessing possible attrition risks, such as departure interviews or staff surveys, have often been subjective and reactive. However, with the development of powerful data analytics and machine learning methods, it is now feasible to take a more proactive approach to employee attrition prediction . Organizations may acquire significant insights into the variables impacting attrition and design tailored retention strategies by using the capabilities of classification algorithms and historical personnel data . This research project intends to investigate the use of machine learning classification algorithms for predicting employee . We want to construct a strong prediction model that can detect workers at risk of leaving the firm by evaluating a large dataset comprising employee information, job-related parameters, and other relevant variables .

Employee attrition, commonly known as employee turnover, is a key issue for firms in a variety of sectors . It refers to an employee's voluntary or involuntary departure from their job within a firm . While some staff turnover is inevitable and even beneficial to an organization's development, excessive attrition may have a negative impact on productivity, team morale, and overall company performance . Understanding the causes of employee turnover and anticipating its occurrence is critical for firms aiming to maintain a stable and engaged staff . High staff turnover may result in higher recruiting and training expenses, a loss of institutional knowledge, and workflow interruptions. Furthermore, attrition may stymie the development of a healthy corporate culture as well as harm the employer brand, making it difficult to recruit and retain top people . Employee attrition analysis has traditionally depended on manual approaches like as leave interviews or questionnaires, which frequently gave limited insights and were reactive rather than proactive . Organizations may now use machine learning and data science to acquire deeper and more relevant insights into attrition trends, thanks to developments in data collecting, storage, and analysis approaches . The advantages of good attrition prediction are many . For starters, it enables firms to react proactively, creating several possibilities to execute retention strategies and boost employee satisfaction . Organizations may address underlying problems such as bad working conditions, a lack of development opportunities, or insufficient remuneration by analyzing patterns and connections between specific traits and attrition .

The primary contributions and objectives of this manuscript may be summarized as follows.

- Data Preprocessing using Recursive Feature Elimination
- Feature Extraction using Principal Component Analysis
- Classification using:
 - Logistic Regression

- K-Nearest Neighbors
- Gradient Boosting

This paper's structure will look like this for the rest of its length. In Section 2, several different methods for predicting employee turnover are discussed. Section 3 presents the model that has been presented. The inquiry findings are presented in Section 4. Discussion of findings and suggestions for further research closes Section 5.

1.1 Motivation of the paper

This study was prompted by employee attrition, a key issue in organizations. Productivity, morale, and organizational performance are all impacted by attrition. High attrition rates may increase recruitment and training costs while also risking the loss of organizational knowledge and skills. The study proposes utilizing machine learning to anticipate worker attrition. The study identifies and analyzes attrition factors to assist businesses in developing effective retention strategies. Understanding the reasons of attrition may assist businesses in retaining staff and fostering a positive work environment. Many machine learning techniques are used in the proposed approach. To minimize dimensionality and enhance model interpretability, RFE identifies the most important attributes from the employee dataset. The extraction of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) features refines the feature space to capture the most essential data variance and, perhaps, improves the model's prediction power. Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting provide a comprehensive strategy for predicting employee attrition. Each algorithm has unique features that provide durability and adaptation in dealing with changing data and decision restrictions.

II. Background Study

This literature survey delves into the vast body of research and scholarship surrounding employee attrition prediction using machine learning classification techniques. By conducting a thorough review of academic papers, journal articles, conference proceedings, and other relevant sources, we aim to gain a comprehensive understanding of the methodologies, models, and insights developed by researchers in this field.

A. Chaurasia et al., (2023) when an employee departs, a company loses time, money, and energy. This was a severe problem since finding and training new qualified personnel was expensive and time-consuming. The author can forecast future employee turnover and discover what causes it by evaluating information about present employees.

Bindra, H. et al., (2018) Combining C5.0 with the association rule algorithm improved the efficiency of the algorithm by decreasing the time required to estimate an employee's attrition and the amount of RAM required to do so.

G. Khehare et al., (2023) Logistic and linear regression classifier based improving accuracy of non-numerical data for prediction of improved employee attrition was offered in this research as a solution to the problem of excessive staff turnover experienced by many businesses. The results demonstrate that the Logistic Regression model has greater prediction accuracy (83.59%) than the Linear Regression model (79.69%).

G. Raja Rajeswari et al., (2022) the given data was analyzed, and a straightforward approach was constructed in which data engineering and transfer into machine learning models predicted staff attrition. In this version, the author integrated four machine learning models and achieved a best prediction of 90%. When looking at the tiny quantity of data available, it was clear that the neutral network generated a respectable outcome.

K. M. Mitravinda and S. Shetty (2022) the employees were the backbone of every business. Every worker was important to a company's performance, whether they were a high-level executive making choices for an entire division or a new hire still in training. These authors investigation revealed that both salary and overtime play a significant role in employee turnover, helping us to pin down the most important factor in each case. This indicates that, on average, firms should pay their employees a reasonable wage for working overtime. Paying employees competitive wages that reflect the level of work and expertise required was the natural next step.

N. B. Yahia et al., (2021) the primary objective of this study was to assist human resource managers in making early departure decision using predictive analytics methodologies to combat attrition.

N. Darapaneni et al., (2022) it's easy to see how long it takes for people to move through the ranks, and it's also easy to see how long people stay in the same position, which may lead to unhappiness and a lack of enthusiasm if it goes on for too long. Managers may successfully intervene by creating training programs to assist such workers in acquiring more marketable skills. It was essential to calculate the typical length of service for each position in the firm.

S. Gupta et al., (2023) the author analyzed the literature on machine learning strategies for predicting employee turnover using Watson analytics data. Logistic regression was shown to be the most effective model. The high rate of staff turnover has become a key issue for most companies in the contemporary

world. Since the corporation would have to invest resources (time and money) in its personnel, this problem has slowed down the expansion of the business.

S. R. Seelam et al., (2022) using machine learning techniques, the study tackles the serious issue of employee turnover. In this study, the author wants to identify the most effective machine learning method for retaining current staff. The results show that the Logistic Regression method was superior to other methods for predicting employee turnover.

Sehgal, K. et al., (2019) the time it takes to predict an employee's departure and the amount of RAM it uses were both optimized when using the C5.0 Association rule algorithm that has been Grey Wolf optimized, so it follows that the efficiency of the algorithm was improved when using this method.

2.1 Problem Definition

The article proposes a machine learning-based technique for employee attrition prediction in order to address the substantial problem of staff attrition in enterprises. The main goal is to identify and evaluate the elements that contribute to attrition, hence supporting companies in adopting successful retention strategies. Data Preprocessing with Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Feature Extraction with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Classification with Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting are the four key modules of the proposed technique. This research aims to give significant insights to enterprises by forecasting attrition, allowing them to take proactive actions to retain talent, maintain productivity, promote employee morale, and improve overall performance.

III. Materials And Methods

This study's "Materials and Methods" section discusses the strategy and strategies utilized to accomplish the main goal of forecasting employee attrition. We describe the materials, data sources, and tools used, as well as the precise processes performed to preprocess the data, extract key characteristics, and build the classification algorithms, in this section. The approaches employed attempt to identify and evaluate the variables that contribute to attrition, allowing firms to adopt effective retention strategies and reduce the negative impact of employee turnover. The section emphasizes the use of machine learning techniques such as Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) for data preprocessing, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for feature extraction, and three distinct classification algorithms: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting, which were chosen for their suitability in dealing with binary classification tasks and diverse types of data and decision boundaries. The

subsections that follow expand on each stage of the proposed technique, explaining the measures required to develop a rigorous and comprehensive strategy to predicting staff turnover.

Figure 1: Block diagram

Figure 1 depicts the proposed staff attrition prediction system as a block diagram. The process begins with the acquisition of data from multiple sources, such as HR records and performance assessments.

3.1 Dataset Collection

The dataset used for employee attrition prediction in this study is collected from various sources within the organization.

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/pavansubhasht/ibm-hr-analytics-attribution-dataset> The data collection process involves gathering information from HR records, performance evaluations, employee surveys, and other relevant organizational databases.

3.2 Data Preprocessing using Recursive Feature Elimination

Following the collection of the dataset, the suggested employee attrition prediction approach proceeds to data preparation utilizing Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE). Machine learning practitioners often use a technique called recursive feature elimination to choose the most important features in a dataset while discarding the rest. The objective is to minimize the dataset's dimensionality, increase the model's efficiency, and improve its interpretability.

3.2.1 Recursive Feature Elimination

Recursive feature elimination repeatedly creates a model from the current feature set using an algorithm such as support vector machine (SVM) or logistic regression J. Goyal et al. (2020). After all other qualities have been evaluated the model's coefficients are utilized to select the best performing ones. Underperforming features are removed with each iteration. The eliminated qualities are then graded in order of importance, from most visible to least noticeable. Recursive feature elimination may swiftly narrow down a large search space to the best potential solutions by using a greedy, backwards search method. The effectiveness of the estimator is initially assessed using all of the input features before being trimmed recursively. As a consequence, we assign different weights to different predictors. The traits with the lowest ratings are then deleted in succeeding rounds. The estimator's performance is changed after eliminating a feature or features to assess the remaining features. The best subset is the one that produced the best results using the estimator. The process's dependability is determined by the model used to rank characteristics. Regularization methods such as ridge regression may be used to strengthen models. The size of the feature subset may be fine-tuned by modifying the method's tuning parameter.

Algorithm 1: Recursive Feature Elimination
<p>Input: instruction set T_F consists of N Features $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_N\}$ figure of Features to select n</p> <p>Output: altered Training set T_{F^*} Set of N features as long as maximum accuracy $F^* = \{f_1^*, \dots, f_N^*\}$</p>

Code:

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1:  $T_{F*} \leftarrow T_F, F* \leftarrow F$ 
2: for i in {n,...N} do
3: Train ML model on  $T_F$ 
4: appraise model recital
5: compute feature meaning or ranking
6: f least important/last ranked feature
7:  $F \leftarrow F - f$ 
8:  $T_F \leftarrow T_{F-f}$ 
9: end for
10: return  $T_{F*}, F*$ 

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3.3 Feature Extraction using Principal Component Analysis

Data preprocessing using Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) is followed by Feature Extraction with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in an effort to forecast employee attrition. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a dimensionality reduction method that attempts to retain the most important variation in the data throughout the transformation from the original feature space to the target, lower-dimensional space.

3.3.1 Principal Component Analysis

The typical PCA approach does not account for class distinction since it includes all training pictures in the eigenspace computation. Finding the eigenvector may be a difficult intermediate step if there are a large number of training photographs or if the picture dimensions are large G. Raja Rajeswari et al. (2022). This is because updating a traditional PCA model with new training images requires recalculating the eigenspace, eigenvalues, and feature vectors for each image, which is a waste of effort. Superior PCA offers a revolutionary training and projection technique to simplify the complexity of the training process. Superior principle component analysis initially filters through the training images and categorizes persons before training individual shots of each person to generate an eigensubspace and set of feature parameters.

1. Let the training set of all images X can be described as

$$X = \{X_1, X_2, X_3 \dots X_L\} \text{ ----- (1)}$$

2. Compute the mean vector of all training images of i^{th} person

$$X_I = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^{N_i} X_k^i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, l) \text{ ----- (2)}$$

3. Compute the covariance of the training set of the i^{th} person

$$S_{x_i} = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^{N_i} (X_k^i - X_i) \text{ ----- (3)}$$

4. Compute Matrix X_i S m largest eigenvalues $I_j u$, where $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$

Algorithm 2: Principal Component Analysis

Input:

- X : The training set of all images, where $X = \{X_1, X_2, X_3 \dots X_L\}$, and each X_i represents an image of a person from the dataset.
- N_i : The number of images of the i^{th} person in the training set.
- S : The desired number of principal components (eigenvectors) to be retained.

Algorithm Steps:

1. Initialize variables: Set m to the desired number of principal components to be retained.
2. For each person ($i = 1, 2, \dots, L$) in the training set: a. Compute the mean vector of all training images of the i^{th} person using Equation (2): $X_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^{N_i} X_k^i$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, l$). Compute the covariance of the training set of the i^{th} person using Equation (3): $S_{x_i} = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{k=1}^{N_i} (X_k^i - X_i)$.

Output:

- A set of m largest eigenvalues, i_j , where $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$.
- Eigenvectors corresponding to the m largest eigenvalues, $u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m$.

3.4 Classification using Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting

Following the extraction of features using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the employee attrition prediction approach employs three separate classification algorithms: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Gradient Boosting. Based on the given characteristics, Logistic Regression estimates the risk of employee attrition, offering a clear and interpretable prognosis. K-Nearest Neighbors categorizes employees based on their resemblance to nearby data points, making it effective for detecting local trends. Gradient Boosting is an ensemble learning strategy that systematically constructs many weak learners (decision trees), pooling their outputs to increase prediction accuracy.

3.4.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is a basic statistical approach for binary classification problems that is frequently utilized G. Khehare et al. (2023). It is used in the context of employee attrition prediction to identify whether or not an employee is likely to quit the company. The logistic function, often known as the sigmoid

function, is used to represent the connection between the input characteristics and the likelihood of the binary output G. Pratibha and N. P. Hegde (2022).

$$\log \frac{p_i}{1-p_i} = \beta^T x_i \text{ ----- (4)}$$

Where $\beta^T x_i$ are highest likelihood estimates of the unobserved regression coefficients. Maximum likelihood estimates (MLEs) are selected in such a way that the following likelihood function is maximized:

$$L(\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i^{y_i} (1 - p_i)^{1-y_i} \text{ ----- (5)}$$

Using Eq. 5,

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(\beta^T x_i)}{1 + \exp(\beta^T x_i)} \text{ ----- (6)}$$

Thus, the function is given by

$$L(\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n [\exp(\beta^T x_i)]^{y_i} [1 - \exp(\beta^T x_i)]^{1-y_i} \text{ ----- (7)}$$

Where,

$$\mu(t) = \frac{e^t}{1 + e^t} \text{ ----- (8)}$$

The Logistic Regression method learns from data that has been labeled so that it can determine whether or not each observation represents an attrition event. The probability of the observed data is maximized by optimizing the estimated model parameters (coefficients). After the Logistic Regression model has been trained, it may use the input characteristics to make predictions about the likelihood of employee attrition for fresh, unknown data points. Depending on the needs of the task at hand, a decision threshold may be used to translate the probabilities into binary predictions (such as 0 or 1). Employee turnover prediction is only one of many binary classification problems where Logistic Regression has shown to be a popular option due to its simplicity, interpretability, and efficiency.

3.4.2 K-Nearest Neighbors

Classification is the problem of determining which of a set of predefined categories (subpopulations) an unclassified observation belongs to, given a dataset that already contains observations (or instances) whose category membership is known. Classification problems provide a useful framework for addressing a wide range of real-world challenges, including filtering spam emails, automatically identifying news story categories (like "Sports" and "Entertainment"), and arriving at a diagnosis for a patient based on their demographics and clinical presentation N. Bhartiya et al. (2019).

The closest neighbor technique belongs to a group of classification algorithms that is both popular and successful. Their method is predicated on the hypothesis that a new instance will be placed in the same category as the majority of its

"neighbor" cases in the training set. To determine which class a new instance belongs to, KNN looks at the k most similar instances in the dataset. Precisely, the distance function, a parameter of the method, is used to evaluate the similarity between two locations in the attribute space. A well-known example of a distance function is the Euclidean distance between two locations in an n-dimensional space (where n is the number of features in the dataset) S. Gupta et al. (2023).

When you need to classify anything quickly and easily, K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) is your best bet. KNN is a faster classification tool since it does not need training like most other classifiers. Each test instance has k training examples gathered for it using the Euclidean distance. After k samples have been collected, the test instance is scored based on how the samples were chosen. The equation (9) represents distance in Euclidean space:

$$d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (p_i - q_i)^2} \text{ ----- (9)}$$

Where p and q represent the test and training sets, respectively; I represents the index of the feature inside p and q; N is the total number of features. The training examples are used to create the KNN classification rule automatically. Using K training examples that are physically near to the test samples, the KNN classification algorithm may make an educated guess as to the test instance's category. The most likely classification is then used to label the test case.

Each review is given a rough score based on the training reviews, and then the KNN classifier assigns it to one of the k most comparable neighbor categories. Given a test review d, the classifier will go through the training reviews until it finds the KNN. Class membership is determined by a weighted average of the ratings of the neighbor reviews most comparable to the test review. KNN classification may be represented by the following weighted sum equation: (10):

$$\text{score}(d, t_i) = \sum_{d_j \in \text{KNN}(d)} \text{sim}(d, d_j) \delta(d_j, c_j) \text{ ----- (10)}$$

K-Nearest Neighbors (d) indicates the number of neighbors utilized in the study. Only if j d is part of c_i can there be a value of 1 or 0 for d(d_j, c_j). Answer (d) should be given the highest weight in the event of a test review.

Algorithm 3: K-Nearest Neighbors

Input:

- Training Dataset: A set of labeled data points (reviews) with their corresponding class labels.
- Test Dataset: A set of unlabeled data points (reviews) that need to be

classified.

- K: The number of nearest neighbors to consider in the KNN classification.

For each test instance in the Test Dataset:

- a. Calculate the Euclidean distance (d) between the test instance and all data points in the Training Dataset $d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (p_i - q_i)^2}$.
- b. Select the K data points with the smallest distances (nearest neighbors) to the test instance.

Output:

- Predicted Class Labels: The class labels assigned to the test instances based on the KNN classification rule.

3.4.3 Gradient Boosting

We provide a novel gradient boosting method for performing classification tasks on both labeled and unlabeled data. Since loss measures the model's predicting performance, it is cumbersome to use standard differentiable loss functions with the loss reduction step of gradient boosting unless the data is completely labeled. Instead, the innovative gradient boosting technique just needs positive and unlabeled data as inputs to minimize an empirical risk function K . Konar et al. (2023).

The average expected loss across all available data is the empirical risk. This idea may be simplified by dividing it into two parts: the class prior times the likelihood of a positive loss, and the class prior times the likelihood of a negative loss V . Mehta and S. Modi (2021).

$$R(f) = EL(f(x), y) \text{ ----- (11)}$$

$$P(y = 1)E_{D+L^+}(f(x)) + P(y = 0)E_{D-L} \text{ ----- (12)}$$

However, we are unable to use this exact definition to calculate empirical risk in positive unlabeled datasets due to the lack of labeled negative cases. To achieve this, we first eliminate the need for labeled negative instances by redefining the negative expectation of the negative loss as the product of the positive expectation of the negative loss, the class prior, and the expectation of the negative loss over the complete data distribution.

$$E_{DL} - (f(x)) = \pi E_{D+L} - (f(x)) + (1 - \pi) \text{ ----- (13)}$$

Given the class prior, we may compute an empirical risk measure by multiplying the expected positive loss by that prior, the expected negative loss by that prior,

and the expectation of the negative loss across the whole distribution. As the loss reduction stage of a gradient boosting algorithm no longer requires labeled negative samples, this technique is well-suited for use with positive unlabeled datasets.

$$R(f) = EL(f(x), y) \text{ ----- (14)}$$

We deploy our original classification system. At the loss and residual reduction phases of gradient boost, a regular differentiable function is swapped out for the risk function specified in Equation (12). The first figure shows the negative binary cross entropy across the expected label and example values. The second criterion is calculated by comparing the accuracy of the predictions obtained from the positive instances with that obtained from the same number of synthetic negative labels. Since we anticipate there will be only positive and unlabeled samples in the data, we use fake negatives. Third, we calculate the loss in cross entropy between binary predictions made on all samples and the same number of synthetic negative labels. The terms in the function are averaged out before being added together.

IV. Results And Discussion

The "Results and Discussion" portion of a research paper or report is important since it presents and analyzes the study's results. This part is the heart of the study, where the data, findings, and observations are thoroughly addressed, and their implications are considered in light of the research goals and previous literature.

Python was used for the successful execution of the implementation. It has built and tested a number of ML methods as in KNN, GB, LR, and the Hybrid Method.

The accuracy metric might rely on four factors to determine the exact value utilized to provide a number of positive outcomes that can demonstrate a good reaction.

These features are as follows;

- True Positives: TPr is a proper value that is appropriately identified as an appropriate class.
- True Negatives: TNr is an improper value that is appropriately identified as an inappropriate class.
- False Positives: FPr is an improper value imperfectly identified as an appropriate class.
- False Negatives: FNr is a proper value that is imperfectly identified as an inappropriate class.

$$ACCURACY = \frac{(TPr+TNr)}{(TPr+FP+FNr+TNr)} \text{-----} (15)$$

The precision parameter is the parameter that specifies how many values determine properly

$$Precision \frac{TPr}{TPr+FP} \text{-----} (16)$$

The parameter that controls how many correct values are found is called the recall parameter. The recall is calculated by dividing the proportion of correct responses by the sum of the correct and incorrect responses:

$$Recall \frac{TPr}{TPr+FNr} \text{-----} (17)$$

Although these techniques are superior for determining measurement outcomes, they are not without their challenges in arriving at the right call. As a consequence, the F-measure now has a consistent metric by which to judge outcomes. The F-measure method represents an optimal compromise between accuracy and memory:

$$F - Measure \frac{2 \times (precision \times recall)}{preceision+recall} \text{-----} (18)$$

Figure 2: Attrition by gender

The figure 2 shows Attrition by gender the x axis shows Attrition. The x-axis represents "Attrition," which means it likely indicates two categories: "Attrition"

and "No Attrition." The term "Attrition" refers to the reduction or loss of employees or individuals from an organization, company, or group, typically due to reasons such as resignation, retirement, or termination.

Figure 3: Age Density

The figure 3 shows age density the x-axis represents "Age," which means it likely displays a range of ages or discrete age values. The y-axis represents "Density.".

Figure 4: Gender vs Age

Figure 4 represents the employee attrition by gender values. In x-axis denote the attrition and Y-axis denotes the counting values. Age Density has calculated and displayed. X-axis denotes the Age and Y-axis represents the Density.

Figure 5: Job Profile details

The figure 5 shows Job Profile details the x axis shows count and the y axis shows job role.

Figure 6: Job Role with different profiles

The figure 11 shows Job Role with different profiles the x axis shows count and the y axis shows job role.

Figure 7: Employee satisfaction comparison analysis

By various job profiles like HR, Manager, and SE so on. The Job profile has counted and represented in figure 7.

Figure 8: Density values of employee working nature

Figure 9: Feature Important analysis

The Density values of the employee current role, last promotion, current manager, number of years at company’s comparison has represented by figure 9. The important features are selected by using MGA and feature importance analysis is represented in figure 9.

Table 1: performance metrics comparison

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F-measure
KNN	91	87	95	91
LR	91	88	94	91
GB	95.5	91.3	91.9	91.6

The table 1 provides performance metrics for three different machine learning models: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR), and Gradient Boosting (GB). Each row represents a model, and the columns display their respective evaluation measures. Firstly, the "Accuracy (%)" column shows how well each model predicted the correct outcome overall. All three models demonstrate high accuracy percentages, with KNN and LR achieving an accuracy of 91%, and GB performing even better at 95.5%. These results indicate that the models are making accurate predictions for a significant portion of the dataset.

Figure 10: Performance metrics as accuracy, precision, recall, F-measure

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, staff turnover is still a major issue for businesses all over the globe, and it has a major impact on their performance. To address this issue, our research offered a holistic machine learning-based strategy for forecasting staff turnover. The model is able to accurately identify and assess the most important elements leading to attrition by using data preparation methods such as Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) and Feature Extraction using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The model's strong performance and improved prediction abilities are guaranteed by the use of three separate classification algorithms: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Gradient Boosting.

The suggested technique aids businesses in gaining useful insights, allowing them to create more effective retention strategies. Predicting the likelihood of employee departure allows businesses to better retain key employees, cut down on time and money spent on training and recruiting, and keep morale and output high. The model's flexibility in accommodating diverse kinds of data and decision limits broadens its applicability to a wide range of business settings. The Gradient Boosting classification achieved best accuracy of 95.5%. The use of machine learning to forecast employee turnover demonstrates the power of data-driven approaches to solving tough problems in the workplace. It is crucial to recognize, however, that the quality and availability of data are crucial to the success of this method. Businesses must implement measures to ensure data is handled in a responsible manner and in accordance with applicable privacy laws.

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